

WOMEN IN SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: SCIENCE AND QUALITY EDUCATION

3RD INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

CHET TILI O'QITISHDA MASOFAVIY TA'LIMNING MUAMMOLARI VA YECHIMLARI

Feruz Ergasheva

Ассистент

Jizzax Politehnika Instituti

feruzaergasheva79@gmail.com

Kalit	so'zlar:	Annotatsiya:
xarakteristikalar, elektron platformalar, texnologiyalari, pedagogika.	chet tili, darsliklar, keys zamonaviy	Maqolada amaliy fanlar universitetlarida chet tili darslarida masofaviy o'qitishning ayrim muammolari ko'rib chiqiladi. Bu muammolar atroflicha tahlil qilinib, ularni hal qilish yo'llari zamonaviy o'quvchilarni sinfda o'qitish, ayniqsa, ingliz tilini o'qitish nuqtai nazaridan bayon etilgan.

PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS OF DISTANCE LEARNING IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

Key words:	Abstract:
characteristics, foreign language, electronic textbooks, platforms, case technologies, modern pedagogy.	The article deals with some problems of distance learning in foreign language classes at universities of applied sciences. These problems are analyzed in detail and their possible solutions are described from the point of view of teaching modern students in the classroom, especially teaching the English language.

ПРОБЛЕМЫ И РЕШЕНИЯ ДИСТАНЦИОННОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ В ОБУЧЕНИИ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ

Ключевые слова:	Аннотация:
характеристики, иностранный язык, электронные учебники, платформы, кейс-технологии, современная педагогика.	В статье рассматриваются некоторые проблемы дистанционного обучения на занятиях по иностранному языку в вузах прикладных наук. Подробно анализируются эти проблемы и описываются возможные пути их решения с точки зрения обучения современных студентов на занятиях, особенно обучения английскому языку.

Modern pedagogy offers the following solutions to this problem. Pupils and teachers can use the possibilities of the latest information technologies, for example, distance learning, when teachers and pupils are separated in terms of location and sometimes time. In addition, there are several other problems whose solution also lies in the integration of digital distance learning technologies. The authors emphasize the correct organization of the process of distance learning, which itself is ambiguous and has its characteristics. Undoubtedly, distance learning is not a very common teaching method in most universities. The organization and management of the educational process often call into question the level of knowledge and competence of foreign language teachers. The authors claim that the main difficulty is that this process has a dual structure. The teacher must not only correctly present material about a foreign language, but also pay attention to how deeply the students have acquired it. The authors explain the benefits of such instruction and consistently justify the need to use all types of language activities. The authors suggest possible exercises for a specific type of activity. The language learning control and monitoring system for all types of language activities are detailed, emphasizing the nature of distance learning. The use of electronic textbooks, platforms, and case technologies is also described in the article. Audio and telephone conferences are also integrated into the teaching process. In this way, distance learning undoubtedly becomes a competitive form of education. This method can be applied to the study of foreign languages, especially English. Global and rapid technological development and expansion of all levels of knowledge in various fields of human activity have a direct impact on the formation of modern education. It is impossible to meet the current knowledge needs of modern students with only traditional forms of the educational environment. Many students, working and studying at the same time, do not have enough time for a qualitative study of the necessary materials, the opportunity to attend lectures and seminars, read additional literature, and prepare for exams on time. Another serious problem with teaching in groups (typical for all universities)

is the inability of individual students to deal with new material in the presence of other fellow students.

Psychological and personal causes are compulsion and fear of incompetence or stupidity, underdeveloped ability to perceive the material quickly. Such students try very hard to perceive and process the material in class. A possible solution to this situation is the implementation of an individual approach, that is, it is necessary to devote part of the time to teaching foreign languages to these students. This means that individual face-to-face work with such students is mandatory. At the same time, teachers should take into account that the implementation of individual work must not be at the expense of other students who master the material more easily and quickly. To solve such problems in modern pedagogy, the possibilities of information technology are used, namely, distance learning. Distance learning enables distance learning in conditions where teachers and students are physically separated. But the real problem is the correctness of the organization of distance learning itself. Since distance learning is a relatively new teaching method in most universities, the process of organizing and building the educational process using distance learning technologies is a real test of the level of knowledge and competence of teachers in foreign language teaching. Difficulties arise because it is necessary not only to present lexical, grammatical, and interdisciplinary material in a foreign language but also to ensure that students have learned it to the required level.

METHODOLOGY: The aim of the research carried out in this article is to characterize the content of distance learning at the university in terms of its type and organizational structure. The research methods are the theoretical analysis and synthesis of scientific information on the subject under consideration, and the generalization of the experience of evaluating distance learning at the university. The problem of distance education is attracting more and more attention from scientists today. The study of foreign language distance learning methods is devoted to the work of such foreign and Russian scientists as Keegan D., Rowntree

D., Lfskog A, & Zaichenko T, Akhayan, AA, Dmitrieva, E.I., Polat E.S., & Bukharkina M.V., & Moiseeva, A.E., Gubina L.V., Gutchel S.K., Shcheglova ON, Kameneva N.A., Kalinin D.A., Anyushenkova ON, Arevkina V.T., & Anyushenkova O.N., Chikileva, L.S., KlimovaI. I. & Kalugina O.A. & Khalevina S.N. & Fedulova A.N. & Trubcheninova AA and others.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION: What are the peculiarities of distance learning of a foreign language at a university? Its main feature is the mediated nature of communication between teacher and student and the consequently limited opportunities for their interpersonal interaction. On the other hand, this form of training allows the students to maximize their performance, which is particularly important for university studies since future specialists should be able to organize their cognitive activities independently. Distance learning involves a different form of presentation and interaction between teacher and student. In university education, the students are most likely to have a conscious attitude toward the learning process, the desire for self-education and self-realization as well as sufficient computer skills. In our view, the benefits of distance learning include: - Opportunities for students to choose their own time and place of learning; - Incentive to develop autonomy and self-discipline;

- High level of comfort in the education of students who are burdened by family and work;

- Mobility of the learning process as the materials are available anywhere on any electronic device. In the distance learning system, you can choose several basic ways of delivering information:

- multimedia textbooks, and teaching aids;
- computers and the Internet;
- radio and television;
- communication between teachers and students.

When implementing distance learning of foreign languages, teachers can use case and network technology, telephone conferences to organize communication

with students or to ensure mutual communication between students, e-mail, various chat rooms, and an electronic bulletin board. Activities such as speaking, listening, reading, and writing is an important part of foreign language teaching in higher education. In the context of distance learning of foreign languages, students' work should be organized in such a way that they carry out these activities independently under the guidance of a tutor to develop skills in all aspects of the language. When learning to listen, it is necessary to use not only audio fragments, but also video recordings that contain a series of extra-linguistic and contextual keys that include some important visual elements that facilitate better understanding. A positive effect is an ability to stop and listen again or repeat the material, which allows students to process sounds and images and better understand the material. Multimedia computer programs play an important role in listening comprehension of a foreign language, distance learning, or literacy training, different ways to control the level of comprehension need to be considered.

CONCLUSIONS: In conclusion, we would like to state that a competent didactic and professional development of foreign language distance learning at universities, regular and professional support of the students, their high motivation, the availability of the necessary teaching materials and electronic educational resources can contribute to distance learning foreign languages competitively and efficiently. In distance learning, teachers have every opportunity to teach students all kinds of language activities and develop communicative competence, which is the main goal of foreign language teaching in higher education. The rational use of modern information technologies opens up completely new opportunities in higher education, and in particular for distance learning of foreign languages.

REFERENCES

- [1].D. Keegan, & Jia. Ya. Yuancheng, The study of distance education. Shijiazhuang: Hebei Scientific and Technology Press. 2000.
- [2].D. Rowntree, Exploring Open and Distance Learning. London, 1992.

- [3].E.N Dmitrieva., G. Kuritsyna, The assessment content of the quality of distance education at a higher education establishment. <http://www.pearsonhighered.com> ISBN-13: 978-0-13-513776-5; ISBN-10: 0-13-513776-4
- [4].E.S. Koplyakova., O.N. Anyushenkova, What types of reading in a foreign language are necessary to pay special attention in non-language higher schools. National Association of Scientists. № 2-5 (7). p. 134-136. 2015.
- [5].E.S. Polat & M.V. Bukharkina, & A. E Moiseeva, New pedagogical and information technologies in the education system: studies. manual for students of higher educational institutions. M.: Publishing Center "Academy", 272 p. ISBN 978-5-7695-4788-1; 2008.
- [6].F.A.Ergasheva.Theory and practice of distance learning and foreign languages teaching.Journal of new Century Innovations.Volume 6.Issue-1_May_2022.p215
- [7]. I. I. Klimova, & O. A. Kalugina, & S. N. Khalevina, & A. N. Fedulova, & A. A. Trubcheninova, Investigating effective foreign language learning design and the implications for distance learning tools. DOI: 10.18355/XL.2017.10.03.22; 2017.
- [8].L.S. Chikileva, Distance learning of foreign languages: advantages and disadvantages // ARTSANAT. The International Virtual Forum «Humanitarian Aspects in Geocultural Space», Istanbul. 2016.
- [9].A.A. Akhayan, Virtual Pedagogical University. Theory of formation. Monograph. Coryphaeus St. Petersburg p.172, ISBN: 5-88891-007-4. 2001.
- [10].A. Löfskog A., T, Zaichenko, From Classroom Teaching to Distance Learning — the Use Different Media, Proceedings of ICDED'94. The First International Conference on Distance Education in Russia. Moskow, p. 133–134; 1994.
- [11].D.A. Kalinin, Difficulties experienced by teachers providing distance learning // Internet magazine “Naukovedenie”, Volume 7, №3 Moscow: Naukovedenie, Available: <http://naukovedenie.ru/PDF/30PVN315.pdf>. 2015.